

EVALUATION OF CARBON AND NITROGEN RATIO ON THE PRODUCTION OF POLYHYDROXYBUTYRATE FROM ACTIVATED SLUDGE THROUGH PARACOCCLUS PANTOTROPHUS

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Abstract

Various microorganisms synthesize and accumulate polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) as energy reserves to survive under nutrient deficient conditions. Since these PHAs are biodegradable, biocompatible and non-toxic so they can serve as potential alternatives to petroleum based plastics, helping to reduce plastic pollution. This research aimed to investigate the impact of C/N ratio on polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB) yield capacity of gram-negative bacterium Paracoccus pantotrophus in activated sludge samples collected from municipal wastewater treatment plants. Activated sludge was cultivated in sequencing batch reactor (SBR) using aerobic dynamic feeding. The PHA content produced was extracted through pretreatment by sodium hypochlorite and then the extracted polymers were purified by using NH₄OH solution and ethanol. The highest PHB yield (2.85 g/L) was obtained when hydroxyphenylacetic acid was used as the primary carbon source at a C/N ratio of 6.1 while acetic acid resulted in a relatively low PHB yield (0.45 g/L) at a C/N ratio of 40. On the other hand, valeric acid at a C/N ratio of 12.1 resulted in the highest biomass concentration (6.1 g/L) while hydroxyphenylacetic acid resulted in the lowest dry cell mass (0.28 g/L) suggesting that carbon type significantly influences metabolic pathways leading to polymer storage. Such an inverse relationship between biomass growth and PHB accumulation highlights the metabolic adaptability of *P. pantotrophus* in response to nutrient limitations. These findings will help enhance industrial strategies for treatment of wastewater and for maximizing microbial PHB bioplastic production capacity.

INTRODUCTION

Products manufactured from plastic have become an integral part of our day to day life however the huge quantities of waste they produce present pressing environmental issues especially in marine ecosystems (Beaumont *et al.*, 2019). Over the last few decades, scientists and industries have become increasingly interested in bio based plastics due to the growing

concern over toxic plastic waste and its significant impact on sustainability thus resultantly considerable efforts are being exerted to synthesize biodegradable plastics particularly polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) (Akaraonye *et al.*, 2010) which can serve as potential alternatives to petroleum based plastic. These bioplastics may also help in building bio-based

economy that can lead to reduction in plastic pollution (Chen *et al.*, 2020).

In the presence of abundant resources and nutrients in environment, majority of living organisms including several bacterial species tend to store essential materials creating reserves that can be used in nutrient limited conditions (Hazer & Steinbüchel, 2007). Wastewater treatment plants frequently use activated sludge systems which consists of a variety of microbial consortium. Through extensive research, it was found that microorganisms in activated sludge tend to adapt to famine and feast periods by producing as well as accumulating polymers like PHAs (Van Loosdrecht *et al.*, 1997). Bacterial species store such PHA polymers in their intracellular granules when nutrients facilitating microbial growth such as sulfur, phosphorous and nitrogen are limited but there is abundance of carbon. As the carbon source starts depleting or deficient nutrient like nitrogen becomes available, PHA begins to depolymerize serving as source of energy and carbon (Tan *et al.*, 2014). Similar to bacteria, plants also possess the capability of synthesizing PHAs as energy reserves but they can only produce up to 10% (w/w) of PHA dry weight but yield greater than this inhibits plant cell growth. On the contrary, bacteria can store up to 90% (w/w) of PHA (Verlinden *et al.*, 2007). Bacteria can produce these biodegradable and biocompatible polymers even from waste carbon sources through which some bacterial species synthesize short-chain length PHAs (Steinbüchel and Fächtenbusch, 1998) like *Bacillus megaterium* (Obruca *et al.*, 2011) and *Cupriavidus necator* (Verlinden *et al.*, 2011). On the other hand, various members of gram negative pseudomonas like *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Pseudomonas putida* tend to produce medium-chain length PHAs when they experience metabolic stress (Prieto *et al.*, 2007). Short chain length PHAs are made up of 3-5 carbon atoms like polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB), medium chain ones are composed of 6-14 carbon atoms and PHAs containing more than 14 carbon atoms are categorized under long chain length PHAs (Prados & Maicas, 2016). The *Paracoccus* genus includes a diverse collection of gram-negative bacteria that are metabolically versatile and adaptable. These bacteria are capable of methylotrophy, denitrification and

production of storage polymers. Several species in this versatile group have been shown to produce polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) like *P. denitrificans* (Yamane *et al.*, 1996), *P. homeinis* (Szacherska *et al.*, 2022) and *P. pantotrophus* (Ucisik-Akkaya *et al.*, 2009). Among these, the facultative methylotroph bacterium *P. denitrificans* has been extensively studied and researched due to its efficient production of poly(3-hydroxybutyrate) (PHB). *P. denitrificans* was found to store up to 72% PHB dry cell weight when glycerol was used as the carbon source (Kalaiyezhini and Ramachandran, 2015). The bacterium under study i.e., *P. pantotrophus* has been found to synthesize PHB in a steady-state culture using solely carbon as substrate (van Leeuwen *et al.*, 1997). Moreover, PHB production was also observed in *P. pantotrophus* using a mixed substrate (Üçisik-Akkaya *et al.*, 2009). The synthesis and accumulation of polyhydroxyalkanoates is influenced by various factors such as the nature of microorganism, rate of growth, type of carbon source, concentration of carbon source, environmental stress factors and fermentation duration. Extensive research on production of polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHA) by bacteria has proposed that concentration and availability of essential nutrients especially the carbon to nitrogen (C/N) ratio have a significant impact on PHA production (Madkour *et al.*, 2013). For example, when *Ralstonia eutropha* was cultivated in the presence of acetic acid, propionic acid, butyric acid as carbon source and ammonium chloride (NH_4Cl) as source of nitrogen at C:N ratio of 80:1, it exhibited maximum PHA production of 70% w/w (Yang *et al.*, 2010). A study on *Haloferax mediterranei* showed that a C/N ratio of 35 led to the highest PHA content up to 47.22% of the cell dry weight (Cui *et al.*, 2017). Similarly, *Bacillus megaterium* showed a high yield of 70% poly-3-hydroxybutyrate when sucrose was used as carbon source and ammonium sulphate ($\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ as source of nitrogen at C:N ratio of 15:1 (Faccin *et al.*, 2009). Literature survey shows that there is lack of research on the impact of C/N ratios on PHA production and growth physiology of *P. pantotrophus*. Understanding this relationship is very important as this understanding can help industries optimize PHA yields by adjusting C/N ratio which can make the

bioplastic production process cost effective and more efficient. This research study aims to understand the impact of varying C/N ratios on microbial growth, PHB production and accumulation by *P. pantotrophus* subsequently leading to the optimization of cultivation strategies for effective biopolymer production.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sludge Source:

Thirty activated sludge samples were collected from six municipal wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) to produce standardized polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHA) and investigate the impact of the carbon-to-nitrogen ratio. The process for producing PHA begins with the selection of biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR) using aerobic dynamic feeding. Once the biomass reaches its desired PHA content, it is lyophilized and moved to the extraction stage. In this phase, PHA is recovered using an advanced extraction method from the bacterial cells, which is detailed below.

Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) Setup and Operation for PHA Production:

Activated sludge from a municipal wastewater treatment plant was cultivated in a 20-liter sequencing batch reactor (SBR) with a 16 L stainless steel tank was used, equipped with a mechanical stirrer and an air diffuser for aeration to treat wastewater. This wastewater had an average chemical oxygen demand (COD) of 2,500 mg/L and contained xenobiotic branched carboxylic acids and ketones. To support bacterial growth in the activated sludge, ammonium chloride was added at a concentration of 0.48 g/L, achieving a carbon-to-nitrogen (C:N) mass ratio of 20, which is essential for normal bacterial synthesis. Each 24-hour cycle consisted of four phases: a 15-minute idle phase where 8 L of mineral medium was added, a 1358-minute aerobic reaction phase with three evenly spaced pulses of a carbon source (a synthetic mixture of organic acids emulating fermented OMW) at an organic load of 1.2 g COD L⁻¹ day⁻¹, a 60-minute settling phase, and a 7-minute discharge phase where 8 L of supernatant were removed. The process was automated using LabView software (National Instruments), with pH and temperature allowed to

vary naturally. The sludge retention time (SRT) and hydraulic retention time (HRT) were maintained at 15 days and 2 days, respectively. The carbon source, representing fermented OMW, contained acetic acid (75%), propionic acid (15%), benzoic acid (3.3%), cinnamic acid (3.3%), and hydroxyphenylacetic acid (3.3%) based on chemical oxygen demand (COD). The mineral medium contained (in mg L⁻¹): KH₂PO₄ (54.4), K₂HPO₄ (43.6), NH₄Cl (129.4), MgSO₄ (43.9), MgCl₂·6H₂O (160), CaCl₂·2H₂O (42), NaHCO₃ (30), and allylthiourea (50) to inhibit nitrification. A trace element solution (0.15 mL L⁻¹) included FeCl₃·6H₂O (1500 µg L⁻¹), H₃BO₃ (150), CuSO₄·5H₂O (30), KI (180), MnCl₂·4H₂O (120), Na₂MoO₄·4H₂O (60), ZnSO₄·7H₂O (120), CoCl₂·6H₂O (150), and 68.5 mL L⁻¹ of 0.5 M EDTA. As the reactor stabilized, the nitrogen concentration was gradually reduced, adjusting the C:N mass ratio to 40, 60, 80, 100, 120, and 140 to create varying nutrient deficiencies. Once stable operation was achieved at each ratio, samples were periodically taken during a randomly selected 2-hour reaction cycle. Reactor performance was monitored weekly for TKN, COD (influent/effluent), dry cell mass and PHA content. The system had been running for 350 days, inoculated with activated sludge from a municipal wastewater plant (Montiel-Jarillo *et al.*, 2019).

Sodium Hypochlorite Pre-Treatment for Polymer Extraction:

The intracellular storage polymers (ISPs) were extracted from the cell mass using Freon (1,1,2-trifluoro-1,2,2-trichloroethane) and quantified. To disrupt the cell membrane and facilitate polymer extraction, a sodium hypochlorite pre-treatment was applied. Lyophilized biomass (50–100 mg) was mixed with 5 mL of NaClO (4.7% Cl₂) and heated at 85°C for 1 hour. The mixture was then centrifuged at 5500 rpm for 10 minutes, and the resulting pellet was washed twice with 5 mL of Milli-Q water before proceeding to the next step. The effects of temperature (85°C, 75°C, and 65°C), exposure time (90, 60, and 30 minutes), and NaClO-to-biomass ratio (5 mL:50 mg and 5 mL:100 mg) were also evaluated. Furthermore, the protocol for polymer separation, based on the dissolution of the non-polymeric cellular matrix with NH₄-laurate, followed

the method by (Mannina *et al.* 2019). Gas chromatography was used to analyze intercellular storage polymers composition, while microscopy was employed to identify the microbial genera responsible for polymer accumulation.

Purification Post-Treatment:

To purify the polymer released during the dissolution of the non-polymeric cellular matrix, two different solvents were employed: an NH_4OH solution and ethanol. Two distinct purification methods were used for post-treatment. In the first method, the polymer was washed once with 0.1 M NH_4OH solution (1 mL) followed by two washes with ethanol (1 mL each). In contrast, the second method involved a single wash with 0.1 M NH_4OH solution. For both approaches, the washing agent was added to the polymer pellet obtained after the previous centrifugation step. The mixture was vortexed until the pellet was fully dispersed. The purified polymer was subsequently recovered by centrifugation and dried overnight at 60 °C.

Quantification of PHA in Microbial Cells via gas chromatography:

Approximately 10 mL of sludge was mixed with 0.4 mL formaldehyde to stop biological activity. Following Werker *et al.* (2008), samples were centrifuged, lyophilized, weighed, and spiked with benzoic acid as an internal standard. The samples were treated with 1.5 mL of butanol and 10 mL of HCl, incubated at 100 °C for 8 hours, then extracted with hexane and MilliQ water. The organic phase was filtered with 0.22 μm filter paper and analyzed via gas chromatography.

Analysis and Evaluation of Extracted Biopolymers:

The structure, thermal properties, and molecular weight of the extracted biopolymers were analyzed using nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR), thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), and gel-permeation chromatography (GPC), respectively. For chemical structure determination, quantitative ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were obtained using a BRUKER DRX-500 spectrometer. The Bruker TopSpin3.5pl7 software was used to process the NMR spectra. The Calibration of biopolymers

molecular weight was performed using poly methyl methacrylate (PMMA) standards.

Analytical Calculations

PHA Yield:

Fraction of extracted polymer weight to biomass weight

$$\text{PHA Yield} = \text{Extracted Polymer Weight} \times \text{Biomass}$$

PHA Purity:

Proportion of PHA in the extracted polymer:

$$\text{PHA Purity} = \text{Mass of PHA} \times \text{Mass of Extracted Polymer}$$

PHA Amount in Microbial Cells:

Proportion of PHA in the lyophilized biomass:
 $\text{PHA Amount in Microbial Cells} = \text{Mass of PHA} / \text{Mass of Lyophilized Biomass}$

The PHA amount and purity were determined using GC results, while PHA yield was measured gravimetrically. NMR spectra confirmed PHA purity.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Bacterial Identification and PHA Storage Potential:

Microscopy analysis and molecular techniques confirmed that *P. pantotrophus* was the dominant bacterial species responsible for PHB accumulation in the activated sludge samples. Through genotypic analysis, it has been revealed that in *P. pantotrophus* PHA genes are arranged in two separate gene clusters. One of the cluster contains the genes *phaA* and *phaB* while other cluster comprises the genes *phaP*, *phaR*, *phaC*, and *phaZ*, organized in opposite directions and this gene organization was observed to be conserved across *paracoccus* species (Moanis *et al.*, 2024). This species is known for its ability to store PHB under nutrient-limiting conditions, particularly when excess carbon is available. Available literature shows that the observed storage polymers in *P. pantotrophus* are either glycogen or PHA. Moreover, previous studies show that *P. pantotrophus* exhibits glycogen (Dircks *et al.*, 2001) and PHA metabolism (Beun *et al.*, 2000) in both anaerobic and aerobic conditions (Carta *et al.*, 2001). However, it exhibits PHB synthesis and accumulation particularly when acetate serves as the carbon source on the other hand glycogen is synthesized when sugars are supplied as source of carbon (Van Loosdrecht *et al.*, 1997). In

the presence of excess carbon, the storage polymer is typically PHB (van den Eynde *et al.*, 1984). The identification of *P. pantotrophus* aligns with previous reports on its capacity to metabolize a wide range of organic acids, supporting its suitability for PHB production from wastewater-derived carbon sources. The presence of *P. pantotrophus* was further confirmed through gas chromatography and nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) analysis of extracted PHB, which revealed a composition primarily consisting of polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHA) with minor fractions of other PHA monomers.

PHA Yield and Dry Cell Mass across C/N Ratios:

To investigate PHB production, the polymers were extracted and subjected to quantification. PHB accumulation and microbial biomass growth varied significantly depending on the carbon source and the corresponding C/N ratio as shown in Table 1. The highest PHB yield (2.85 g/L) was obtained when hydroxyphenylacetic acid was used as the primary carbon source at a C/N ratio of 6.1 as shown in Figure 1b. Aromatic compounds like hydroxyphenylacetic acid and phenol have been found to be promising carbon sources for PHB synthesis in a variety of microorganisms such as *Pseudomonas* species and various soil bacteria. Such compounds are abundantly present in industrial wastewater serving as a source of biodegradable polymer accumulation. The high PHB yield shown by hydroxyphenylacetic acid at 6.1 C/N ratio suggests that lower C/N ratios and excess of carbon promote intracellular PHB storage, likely due to nitrogen limitation-induced stress in *P. pantotrophus*. Also, the other aromatic acid i.e., cinnamic acid showed a PHB yield of 2.01 g/L at C/N ratio of 9.1. Similarly, in *P. denitrificans* it was observed that for primary alcohols as carbon source PHA was not produced when nitrogen was present in high concentration however nitrogen deficiency in second cultivation stage resulted in considerable amount of polymer accumulation (Kim *et al.*, 1997). During cultivation, as the C/N ratio was increased consequently the PHB content decreased irrespective of the type of carbon source used. On the contrary, in a study it was found that higher C:N ratios in the feed lead to greater PHB accumulation by *Methylobacterium sp. V49* using pure culture when

glucose was supplied as the only carbon source. Additionally, culture supplied with the highest C/N ratio exhibited the highest PHB yields (Ghatnekar *et al.*, 2002). Acetic acid, the most abundant component (75%) in the synthetic carbon mixture, resulted in a relatively low PHA yield (0.45 g/L) at a C/N ratio of 40. Despite its high availability, acetic acid did not significantly enhance PHA accumulation, suggesting that carbon type influences metabolic pathways leading to polymer storage. The PHB accumulation reached a plateau in the later half most probably because of the gradual depletion of the different types of carbon source. This results in a condition where carbon is no longer available in excess for PHA production consequently leading the bacteria to rely on stored PHA for maintaining metabolic activities (Zhou *et al.*, 2022).

Effect of Carbon Source on Microbial Growth:

Microbial growth, represented by dry cell mass, followed a different trend from PHA accumulation. Among the tested carbon sources, valeric acid at a C/N ratio of 12.1 resulted in the highest biomass concentration (6.1 g/L) as shown in figure 1A, suggesting that this compound strongly supported bacterial growth. *P. pantotrophus* utilizes pentanoic acid commonly called as valeric acid as a carbon source for its growth. It metabolizes pentanoic acid using β -oxidation cycle which converts this acid into acetyl-CoA and propionyl-CoA. This acetyl-CoA goes into the citric acid cycle for ATP synthesis which is a simple metabolic pathway for medium-chain fatty acids in *Paracoccus* species. Moreover, the availability of medium-chain fatty acids such as valeric acid likely promote cell division and metabolic activity, leading to greater biomass accumulation. Similarly, butyric acid (C/N = 14.6) produced a substantial biomass yield of 4.6 g/L, further supporting the role of short-chain volatile fatty acids (VFAs) in microbial proliferation. In *P. denitrificans*, valeric acid proved to be a good carbon source for PHA synthesis (Kim *et al.*, 1997). In contrast, hydroxyphenylacetic acid, which yielded the highest PHA production (2.85 g/L), resulted in the lowest dry cell mass (0.28 g/L). Nitrogen limitation reduces biomass production as biomass growth requires an adequate amount of nitrogen for growth. This suggests that under lower C/N conditions, microbial metabolism shifts from

active biomass growth to intracellular polymer storage as a survival mechanism. The inverse relationship between biomass growth and PHA accumulation highlights the metabolic adaptability of *P. pantotrophus* in response to nutrient limitations.

Cultivation Strategies and Their Impact on PHA Production:

The cultivation method also influenced PHA yield. One-stage cultivation (as observed with valeric acid, cinnamic acid, and hydroxyphenylacetic acid) tended to produce higher PHA yields, while two-stage processes were more effective in promoting microbial growth, as seen with acetic acid and propionic acid. This finding aligns with previous studies indicating that single-stage cultivation under nitrogen-limited conditions can enhance PHA storage efficiency. Furthermore, a research study proposed that when a

nutrient critical for cell growth is limited in the medium, cells continue to divide in a controlled manner enabling extended PHA storage without actually triggering excessive cellular growth (Kourmentza *et al.*, 2017). Under nitrogen deficiency, various bacterial species store PHA/PHB up to 30% of their dry cell mass. Another research found that fed-batch cultivation under nitrogen limitation achieved PHA/PHB up to 57%. Additionally, cultivation strategies have been studied which under nitrogen limitation combined with carbon feeding in a controlled manner resulted in steady PHA accumulation along with cellular contents reaching up to 74% suggesting that single stage and nitrogen-deficient cultivation is a promising approach to achieve enhanced PHA storage capacity.

Table 1: The effect of different carbon sources and C/N ratios on PHB yield, biomass growth, and cultivation strategy in *P. pantotrophus*.

Carbon source	Concentration (%)	C:N Ratio	PHB Yield (g/L)	Dry Cell Mass (g/L)	Cultivation method
Acetic acid	75	40	0.45	0.98	Two stage
Propionic acid	15	24.2	0.78	2.18	Two stage
Butyric acid	9.1	14.6	1.02	4.6	Two stage
Valeric acid	5	12.1	1.56	6.1	One stage
Benzoic acid	3.3	10.2	1.85	0.89	Two stage
Cinnamic acid	3.3	9.1	2.01	0.54	One stage
Hydroxyphenylacetic acid	3.3	6.1	2.85	0.28	One stage

Figure 1: Effect of C/N ratio on (A) dry cell mass (g/L) (B) PHA yield (mol/mol)

CONCLUSIONS

The findings of this research highlight the relationship between C/N ratio and the PHB accumulation potential of gram negative bacterium *P. pantotrophus* present in activated sludge derived from municipal wastewater. The PHA accumulation patterns as seen from the experiments vary depending upon the C/N ratio. The highest PHA yield (2.85 g/L) was obtained when hydroxyphenylacetic acid was used as the primary carbon source at a C/N ratio of 6.1 which shows that lower C/N ratios promote intracellular PHA storage moreover the PHA accumulation increases under nitrogen deficient conditions in *P. pantotrophus*. Although acetic acid was present in high concentration but it failed to significantly enhance PHA accumulation, suggesting that carbon type influences metabolic pathways leading to polymer storage. Additionally, microbial growth which was represented by dry cell mass followed a different trend from PHA accumulation as valeric acid at a C/N ratio of 12.1 resulted in the highest biomass concentration (6.1 g/L) while hydroxyphenylacetic acid, which yielded the highest PHA production (2.85 g/L), resulted in the lowest dry cell mass (0.28 g/L) suggesting that under lower C/N conditions, microbial metabolism shifts from active biomass growth to intracellular polymer storage as a survival mechanism. This results and findings highlight the metabolic adaptability of *P. pantotrophus* in response to nutrient limitations which present this microorganism as a promising tool for industrial effluent treatment and also as candidate for bioplastic synthesis using industrial wastewater.

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